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Research Article

KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICE OF PNEUMOCOCCAL AND INFLUENZA VACCINES AMONG DIABETIC PATIENTS ATTENDING DIABETIC CLINIC JINNAH HOSPITAL LAHORE

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Abstract:

Background: Immunosuppressed diabetic patients are at an increased risk for developing pneumococcal and influenza infections. Elderly diabetics are advised proper immunization for prevention against them. This study aimed to find the prevalence and factors impeding the results of such vaccinations.

Methods: A survey was conducted after consent via questionnaire solved through the interview method. A total of 200 diabetics were selected on the basis of disease duration, treatment, knowledge and practice of specific vaccination (pneumococcal and influenza) for high risk groups.

Results: The study sample comprised of 200 diabetic individuals > 18 years of age with mean of 47 years. Males comprised 54% of data and females the other 46%. 97 % were married. 41 % were illiterate and the % decreases upon the hierarchy of education reaching 3.5 % post graduates. 60 % were not financially strong and Only 10% were financially strong.

63 % were local while the others being outside the city suburbs. 83 % were unaware of the fact that diabetes can cause immunocompromised state and different recurrent infections. 92 % were not having the information about diabetics being more prone to pneumococcal and influenza infections especially the people above 65 years of age. An ALARMING 98 % people did not have any clue that ANY vaccination is recommended for diabetics. Furthermore, 99 % were unaware of pneumococcal and influenza vaccination for diabetics. Even doctors did not recommend vaccines to 99% of the people

Conclusion: The knowledge and practice of influenza and pneumococcal vaccination in elderly diabetics is drastically low in Pakistan. The foremost barrier is the lack of knowledge among doctors as well as public followed by socioeconomic conditions and perceived decreased benefits of vaccines. The health care providers and government should take concrete steps to cope with the situation. Certain workshops should be carried out to highlight the importance of pneumococcal and influenza vaccines among doctors and they should be advised to inform the public about it. Proper counseling about vaccine benefits should be started and Government should take serious interest in the matter and supply hospitals with such vaccines at diabetic clinics. Media should also participate actively for spreading relevant information regarding vaccination and diabetes.

Keywords: Diabetes, Immunocompromised, influenza, pneumococcal, knowledge, attitude, practice, vaccination.

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INTRODUCTION:

“Diabetes mellitus (DM) refers to a group of common metabolic disorders that share the phenotype of hyperglycemia.”⁽¹⁾ Glucose homeostasis depicts a balance between hepatic glucose production and peripheral glucose uptake and utilization which is regulated by insulin. ⁽¹⁾

Patho physiologically DM is divided into 2 types: “Type 1 diabetes caused by auto immune destruction of insulin producing Beta cells in the pancreatic islets resulting in absolute insulin deficiency whereas Type 2 diabetes is characterized by resistance to the action of insulin and later an inability to produce sufficient insulin to overcome this insulin resistance “⁽²⁾

Individuals with diabetes mellitus have a greater frequency and severity of hazardous infections especially respiratory tract infections because of immunologic deficiencies. ⁽³⁾

Due to this immunosuppressed state, there are chances of many infections like hepatitis B, diphtheria, tetanus, pertusis, zoster and the main ones being pneumococcal and influenza infections. ⁽⁴⁾

Because of having global prevalence of diabetes, the pneumococcal and influenza complications are worldwide.

Prevalence of pneumococcal infections was considerably increased in diabetics. ^(5,6)

Though no age is exempted from pneumococcal and influenza disease but complications due to these are 3-6 folds higher in diabetic patients as compared to non diabetics. ^(7, 8)

Seasonal vaccination of pneumococcal and influenza is recommended by the Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices, Irish Immunization Guidelines and WHO reporting 40-80% drop in the hospitalization of diabetics. ⁽⁹⁻¹²⁾ According to researchers in the Western countries, there is knowledge of pneumococcal vaccination to

35% and for influenza was approximately 80% and practiced by 58% for pneumococcal to 63% for influenza. ⁽¹³⁻¹⁸⁾

According to Asian researches, 53% people knew about the vaccinations but practiced only by 9.8% for pneumococcal to 27% for influenza. ^(9, 12, 17)

2 type of pneumococcal vaccines, Pneumococcal Conjugate vaccine (PCV) given at the minimum age of 6 weeks and Polysaccharide vaccines given at minimum age of 2 years and revaccination after 65 years is recommended. Annual vaccination of trivalent inactivated influenza vaccine (for persons above 6 months) and live attenuated influenza vaccine (LAIV) for 2-49 years old individuals is recommended in diabetics. ^(19, 20)

Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices and CDC has advised the diabetics to take proper immunization as they are at high risk. ⁽²¹⁾

Vaccination can provide cost effective protection, decreased complications, hospitalizations and death rates among diabetics. ^(7, 22)

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A cross sectional study was conducted at Diabetic Clinic of Jinnah Hospital Lahore from April 2017 – June 2017. 200 diabetic patients those fulfilling the inclusion criteria of 18 years or older patients having type 1 or type 2 diabetes diagnosed minimum 1 year earlier were selected through Non-Probability/Purpose sampling technique. Informed consent was taken before every interview. The questionnaire comprised of demographic and socioeconomic details like age, gender, residence, education status, financial status, knowledge about vaccination particularly influenza and pneumococcal, attitude and their practices.

Patients having cognitive impairment, admitted to ICU, emergency departments or psychiatric department were excluded. Diabetes mellitus was diagnosed on basis of abnormally high random glucose levels above 200mg/dl or above. ⁽²⁾

RESULTS:

This study is one of the earliest (if not the first) focusing on knowledge and practices related to different vaccinations, recommended for the elderly diabetics in Pakistan.

TABLE 1 (Patient Demographics)

VARIABLES		Total (n=201)	
		n	%
Sex	Male	109	54.2
	Female	92	45.8
Age	18-30	12	6.0
	30-40	20	10.0
	40-50	40	19.9
	50-60	65	32.3
	60 and above	64	31.8
Marital Status	Married	196	97.5
	Unmarried	5	2.5
Education Level	Illiterate	82	40.8
	Islamic- Education	10	5.0
	Primary	49	24.4
	Intermediate	40	19.9
	Graduation	13	6.5
	Post-Graduation	7	3.5
Income	< 10,000	35	17.4
	10,000-20,000	86	42.8
	21,000-30,000	36	17.9
	31,000-40,000	24	11.9
	>40,000	20	10.0
Resident	Lahore	127	63.2
	North Punjab	53	26.4
	South Punjab	20	10.0
	Other Provinces	1	0.5

The study sample comprised of 200 diabetic individuals > 18 years of ages with SD of 1.18 and mean of 47 years.

TABLE 2 : Relation among Duration of diabetes and information about immunocompromised state, recurrent infections and diabetes control

Duration	Diabetes control		Recurrent Infections		Immunocompromised info	
	Good	poor	Yes	No	Yes	No
Within 5 yrs	48	27	27	48	13	62
5-10 ys	40	16	23	33	09	47
10-15 yrs	12	17	13	16	01	28
15-20 yrs	07	12	10	09	05	14
20 +	02	20	12	10	06	16
Total	109	92	85	116	34	167

Diabetes Control and Tretment

10% had diabetes from 15-20 years and another 11% had it for more than 20 years. Rest were having it for less than 15 years making the SD of 1.34 and a mean of 7 years.

45% had poor control of diabetes having significant HbA1C levels (patients were not aware of HbA1c).

75 % (151) were taking only allopathic medicine and 22 % (44) both allo and homeopathic treatment. From those taking the allopathic medicine, 12 % (25) were taking only insulin injection, 38 % (78) only oral hypoglycemic drugs and 47 % (95) were taking both insulin injection and oral hypoglycemic drugs.

Knowledge and Practice

83 % (167) were unaware of the fact that diabetes can cause immunocompromised state and different recurrent infections. 92 % (185) were not having the information about diabetics being more prone to pneumococcal and influenza infections especially the people above 65 years of age.

Table-3
Information about Influenza and Pneumococcal in Diabetes

Status	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	15	7.5
No	186	92.5
Total	201	100.0

TABLE 4 : Relation among age and information about pneumococcal and influenza disease ,any vaccine recommended in diabetes and recommended by doctor

Age	Info Influenza +pneumo disease		Any vaccine		Recommended by DR.	
	YES	NO	Yes	No	Yes	No
18-30 yrs	00	12	00	12	00	12
30-40 ys	01	19	01	19	01	19
40-50 yrs	05	35	01	39	00	40
50-60 yrs	03	62	01	64	01	64
60 n above	06	58	00	64	00	64
Total	15	186	03	198	02	199

An ALARMING 98 % (196) people did not have any clue that ANY vaccination is recommended for diabetics. Furthermore, 99 % (198) were unaware of pneumococcal and influenza vaccination for diabetics. Even doctors did not recommend vaccines to 99% of the people.

Graph-1 Information About Pneumococcal and Influenza Vaccine

information about pneumococcal and influenzal vaccine

99 % (198) people had no information on pneumococcal or influenza vaccination, so they did not come to practice it. 1% who had knowledge were practicing according to schedule of vaccines. That 1 % (foreign visitors) had information from newspaper and specialized doctors in private set ups. Approximately 90% people think of vaccination in good terms and consider it beneficial.

45 % (90) people were either not financially strong or had to support large families so they could not afford the vaccines. The vaccine is either not available or very costly. 99 % (198) were willing to take the vaccines if given freely.

Only 1% who were aware of the vaccination process helped to spread this information by advising other diabetics.

More than 99% people blamed the NGOs and Government agencies for not spreading the information regarding pneumococcal and influenza vaccination in diabetics. Otherwise, 52% were satisfied with the other health facilities provided by the government set ups.

DISCUSSION:

This is one of the earliest if not the first research regarding the vaccination status of knowledge and its practices in Diabetics in Pakistan. The purpose was to find out the information about diabetes, its immune compromised state, increased risk of pneumococcal and influenza infections and practice and schedule of its vaccination.

According to the research, 41% of the population is illiterate not even knowing how to write their own name especially the people from the suburbs and south of the province. This illiteracy aided a lot in the non-availability of any kind of knowledge about diabetes. Most of these illiterate people did not have any clue about diabetics being immune compromised or being more prone to pneumococcal and influenza infections. But as we ascended up the hierarchy of education, the information about diabetes became more and more known to patients. A large majority of the educated lot knew about the immune compromised state of diabetics but did not come to know about the pneumococcal and influenza infections. The pneumococcal and influenza infections turned out to be a mystery for almost all the people.

The duration of diabetes also had an impact upon the knowledge people had about their disease. People who had diabetes for more than 10-15 years knew the risks of being immune compromised and having recurrent infections including pneumococcal and influenza infections. People having recent diagnosis did not know about the disease and its risks.

All of the patients were the same when it came to knowledge of immunization in elderly diabetics, not having even the foggiest notion of any recommended vaccines in diabetics. Regardless of the age, sex, education status, residential areas and socioeconomic conditions, all of the people were unaware about the existence of pneumococcal and influenza vaccines for elderly diabetics.

Such is the dilemma of our country that almost all of the medical students and most of the general physicians were also not aware of the fact. Under such circumstances, physicians also did not recommend any vaccines to the elderly diabetics. Some of the people even questioned the beneficial effects of vaccination and some even considered them to be doing more harm than good. When people were unaware of the availability of vaccines, then practice and schedule of practice were out of question.

99% of the patients were lacking the knowledge about adequate information about pneumococcal and influenza vaccination in elderly diabetics and the main reason for it is NON AVAILABILITY of adequate knowledge given by the physicians to the patients. AN ALARMING situation is that even most of the general physicians and almost all of the medical students are also unaware of the vaccination process. Under such circumstances giving proper knowledge to the patients is out of question.

1% of the patients had adequate knowledge about the disease itself, the increased incidence of pneumococcal and influenza infections and also the vaccination and its schedule. Those were either foreign visitors who had this information from abroad or were visiting specialized physicians in private sector. They were also helping to spread this information to other diabetics. Considering the fact that they were foreign visitors, let's move our attention to some of the international researches and their statistical data.

Table 5

Knowledge Region	Practice			
	Pneumococcal(%)	Influenza(%)	Pneumococcal(%)	Influenza(%)
India ^(9,19)	15.0	15.0	8.8	09.0
Singapore	-	59.0	-	24.5
Korea	-	-	18.0	57.0
Turkey ^(9,17)	53.0	53.0	15.0	50.0
Germany ⁽¹³⁾	28.2	79.0	11.5	48.0
America ⁽¹⁶⁾	-	-	65.7	66.0
Canada ^(11,14,15)	87.0	87.0	58.0	58.0
Australia	-	-	31.0	47.0
Spain	-	-	65.0	65.0
Ireland ⁽¹⁰⁾	-	-	22.0	65.0
France ⁽¹⁸⁾	-	-	49.0	59.0

The data shows a large difference between awareness and practice of vaccination between Pakistan and other countries. Most of the countries have awareness greater than our country and significant vaccination rates also. Recent studies shows a remarkable rate of 65% immunization in Spain, 30-47% in Australia and 50% in Turkey.⁽⁹⁾

Apart from recommendations from ACIP(Advisory Committee of Immunization Practices) ,American College of Physicians, The American Academy of Paediatrics,American Academy of Family Physicians, WHO and CDC to provide appropriate knowledge and practices , we are far lacking behind.⁽⁴⁾

Recommended pneumococcal vaccines by different organizations.⁽⁷⁾

Organization	Recommendation	Revaccination
1. American Diabetes Association. ^[19]	All diabetic subjects ≥ 2 years of age.	a. A onetime revaccination is recommended for individuals >64 years of age if the vaccine was administered >5 years ago. b. Other indications for repeat vaccination include nephrotic syndrome, chronic renal disease, and other immunocompromised states, such as posttransplantation.
2. Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices. ^[7]	a. All persons at age 65 years. b. Adults aged 19–64 years with chronic medical conditions like chronic heart disease, chronic lung disease, diabetes mellitus, asthma, etc. c. PPV is recommended for children aged 2 years or older with certain underlying medical conditions, including diabetes mellitus.	a. Those who received PPV before age 65 years for any indication should receive another dose at age 65 years or later if at least 5 years have passed since their previous dose. Those who receive PPV at or after age 65 years should receive only a single dose. b. A second dose of PPV is recommended 5 years after the first dose for persons aged 19–64 years with functional or anatomic asplenia and for persons with immunocompromising conditions c. Single revaccination should be administered after 5 years to children with functional/ anatomic asplenia or immunocompromising condition.
3. Australian Technical Advisory Group on Immunization. ^[20]	a. All persons aged ≥ 65 years b. People aged ≥ 10 years who have underlying chronic illnesses predisposing them to including, acute nephrotic syndrome chronic cardiac, renal or pulmonary disease, diabetes, etc. c. Tobacco smokers.	
4. Canadian National Advisory Committee on Immunization. ^[21]	a. All individuals ≥ 65 years of age b. Children ≥ 5 years of age and adults who have not previously received pneumococcal vaccines should be vaccinated with Pneu-P-23. Pneu-C-7 is not contraindicated in children ≥ 5 years of age with high-risk conditions. ^[21]	
5. The United Kingdom Department of Health. ^[22]	a. All adults over the age of 65 b. Children under the age of 5 who have previously had invasive pneumococcal disease. a. Consider all patients over the age of 2 months with increased risk for the following including type 1 diabetes mellitus, or type 2 diabetes requiring oral hypoglycemic drugs. It does not include diabetes that is diet-controlled.	
6. The Geriatric Society of India. ^[23]	Persons aged 50 years and above.	

Recommended influenza vaccines by different organizations.⁽⁷⁾

Organization	Vaccination
1. American Diabetes Association, Immunization Guidelines 2012. ^[19]	a. Influenza vaccine is recommended annually for all diabetic patients ≥ 6 months of age.
1. CDCs ACIP 2011–12 Influenza Vaccination Guidelines. ^[24]	a. Routine immunization (annual vaccination) is now recommended for anyone ≥ 6 months as soon as vaccine is available. b. Children aged 6 months to 8 years whose vaccination status is unknown or who have never received seasonal influenza vaccine before as well as children who did not receive at least 1 dose of influenza A (H1N1) 2009 monovalent vaccine regardless of previous influenza vaccine history should receive 2 doses of 2010–2011 seasonal influenza vaccine (minimum interval 4 weeks) during the 2010–2011 season.
2. Australian Technical Advisory Group on Immunization. ^[26]	a. All individuals aged 65 years and over. b. All Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples aged 15 years and over c. Pregnant women. d. Individuals aged 6 months and over with medical conditions predisposing to severe influenza including cardiac disease, chronic respiratory disease, diabetes and other metabolic disorders, renal disease, etc.
4. Canadian National Advisory Committee on Immunization for the 2011–2012 Season. ^[27]	a. Influenza vaccine may be administered to people of any age who are residents of nursing homes and other chronic care facilities, people ≥ 65 years of age and healthy children 6–23 months of age. ^[32] b. Adults (including pregnant women) and children with the following chronic health conditions are recommended recipients of Influenza Vaccine like cardiac or pulmonary disorders, diabetes mellitus and other metabolic diseases, renal disease, etc.
5. The United Kingdom Department of Health. ^[28]	a. All individuals aged 65 or over. b. All those aged 6 months or over in a clinical risk group like chronic respiratory disease, heart disease, renal disease, liver disease, diabetes including Type 1 diabetes, Type 2 diabetes requiring insulin or oral hypoglycemic drugs and diet-controlled diabetes.

Although lack of knowledge is the main player, 60% of the population is living end to end and can't afford the appropriate vaccines. Vaccines are either not available easily to mass majority of the population or have very poor cost effectiveness making them almost out of the reach of a common man.

No care is being given to the aforementioned case by the Government and vaccines are not available at most of the government hospitals. Considering the fact 99% patients blamed the Government agencies and NGO's for their lack of knowledge and not spreading the adequate information.

Some of the patients questioned the beneficial effects of vaccines and considered them to do more harm than good. This too was a problem because of the low literacy rate of the country.

CONCLUSION:

The knowledge and practice of influenza and pneumococcal vaccination in elderly diabetics is drastically low in Pakistan. The foremost barrier is the lack of knowledge followed by socioeconomic conditions and perceived decreased benefits of vaccines. The health care providers should educate the patients and government should take concrete steps towards education and improvement of socioeconomic condition of people along with cost effectiveness and availability of vaccines for a common man.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

As lack of knowledge is the prime factor leading to the devastating low rates of vaccines in elderly diabetics, adequate knowledge should be spread all over to improve the standard of living of elderly diabetics. Also the medical students and general physicians be told in workshops about the

recommended vaccination status and they should help in the spread of this information.

Certain steps should be taken by the government agencies and NGO's as well to spread the information across by different sources (newspaper, magazines, and diabetic clinics). Free vaccines should be given in diabetic clinics to be given to the general public to cope this situation..

Literacy rate and general awareness can only be increased by thorough steps in a long term program. Benefits of Vaccines should be told to illiterate people to make them co operate in the vaccination process.

Socioeconomic conditions to be improved on all costs and the cost effectiveness of the vaccines and their availability should be improved to make them in range of common man.

As all of this fuss over diabetes, so we should treat the diabetics with care and the best treatment option available and make them realize the true nature of their disease and its complications.

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